

THE IMPORTANCE OF GRAMMAR TO DEVELOP LANGUAGE COMPETENCE (AS AN EXAMPLE OF ENGLISH)

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Annotation: *This article contains information about the role of grammar learning and teaching in education. How teachers can conduct lessons without boredom and misunderstanding is one of the important issues of this work. Three methods of teaching grammar to school students are analyzed and differed from each other. The investigation also attempts to see which of these three approaches has a positive effect on academic grammar achievement. What are inductive, deductive, and eclectic approaches? What are the advantages and disadvantages have they got? What are the effects of teaching with the help of these methods? How they can be implemented in the process of the lesson? To answer the questions of the study research was made based on them. Only educating grammar in a traditional way like lecturing and copying is how useless in today's classroom. That's why students who learned grammar with modern methods and tools showed greater results rather than others.*

Keywords: *inductive, deductive, eclectic, communicative, elementary, translating, method, approach.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada grammatikani o'rganish va o'qitishning ta'limdagi o'rni haqida ma'lumotlar berib o'tilgan. O'qituvchilar darslarni qanday qilib zerikmasdan va tushunmovchiliklarsiz o'tkazishlari hozirgi zamonning muhim masalalaridan biridir. Maktab o'quvchilariga grammatika o'rgatishning uchta usuli tahlil qilinadi va bir-biridan farqlanadi. Tadqiqotchilar, shuningdek, ushbu uchta yondashuvdan qaysi biri akademik grammatika yutuqlariga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishini topishga harakat qilmoqdalar. Induktiv, deduktiv va eklektik yondashuvlar nima? Ularning qanday afzalliklari va kamchiliklari bor? Ushbu usullar yordamida o'qitish qanday samara beradi? Ularni dars jarayoniga qanday tatbiq qilish mumkin? Yuqoridagi savollariga javob berish uchun ushbu metodlar asosida tadqiqotlar olib borildi. Grammatikani faqat ma'ruza o'qish va kitoblardan nusxa ko'chirish kabi an'anaviy tarzda o'qitish bugungi sinfxona o'quvchilari uchun qanchalik foydasiz ekanligi sharhlab berildi. Shuning uchun grammatikani zamonaviy usul va vositalar bilan o'rgangan talabalar boshqalardan ko'ra yuqori natijalarni ko'rsatdilar.*

Kalit so'zlar: *induktiv, deduktiv, eklektik, kommunikativ, boshlang'ich, tarjima, usul, yondashuv.*

Аннотация: Эта статья содержит информацию о роли изучения и преподавания грамматики в образовании. Как учителям вести уроки без скуки и непонимания – один из важных вопросов этой работы. Анализируются и отличаются друг от друга три методики обучения грамматике школьников. Исследование также пытается выяснить, какой из этих трех подходов оказывает положительное влияние на успеваемость по грамматике. Что такое индуктивный, дедуктивный, эклектический подходы? Какие преимущества и недостатки у них есть? Каковы результаты обучения с помощью этих методов? Как их можно внедрить в процесс урока? Для ответа на вопросы были проведены исследования. Только обучение грамматики традиционными способами, такими как чтение лекций и копирование, настолько бесполезно в сегодняшнем классе. Вот почему студенты, изучавшие грамматику современными методами и инструментами, показали лучшие результаты, чем другие.

Ключевые слова: индуктивный, дедуктивный, эклектический, коммуникативный, элементарный, перевод, метод, подход.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, many language learners and teachers tend to consider that learning grammar while learning English is not so important any longer. Even though some native speakers and educators suppose that teaching grammar for communication and language skills does not play an essential role for students. However, numerous language scholars and linguists support the opinion that grammar is the foundation of language acquisition and an indispensable part of linguistics. The main aim of this article is to investigate the nature of grammar as well as its role to enhance language competence. We are going to discuss the different viewpoints of philosophies about the definition of grammar, how grammar is necessary and beneficial, and the influence of grammar on the teaching process.

METHODS

Grammar, a set of rules, usage of phrases, and putting words together to make sense helps language learners in different ways. It seems to be complex to comprehend, clarify, and describe what grammar is as well as how it should be taught in English language teaching (Ellis, 2006; Brown & Lee, 2015; Richards, 2015). As defined in the Oxford Dictionary, Grammar is the rules in a language for changing the form of words and joining them into sentences. Linguistics is the set of rules that describe the structure of a language and control the way that sentences are formed with errors in spelling and grammar. Most students find learning grammar quite difficult as well as

for some teachers teaching it is more challenging. Initially, only learning grammar may seem boring and does not bring students' attention. Therefore, interactive and communicative approaches should be implemented during the lesson process. There are some tips and techniques for pedagogy recommended by specialists. It is generally admitted that there are four skills in any language: speaking, listening, reading, and writing. Learners in foreign language situations need to learn and master these skills in order to develop language acquisition. Grammar and vocabulary are language components that are the fundamental basis. For example, if a student does not know grammar well, he or she cannot speak fluently or without mistakes. While writing an essay or text without enough grammar knowledge, the writer may lose the meaning and fluency of the written work. According to Fischer (2015), language without grammar would be chaotic. It is impossible to describe a language without seeking its underlying framework. Before starting to teach grammar, teachers are suggested to pay attention to students' age, personality, language proficiency, motivation, interest, and even culture.

Approaches in Teaching Grammar

Abdullah and Shah (2014) also stated that the study of grammar allows language users to analyze patterns and avoid making mistakes. In this way, it can lead to more accurate writing and speaking skills among the students. In fact, there are three approaches to grammar teaching: **Inductive, Deductive, and Eclectic.**

***Inductive approach**

This type of approach is like a logical process that involves using specific experiences, observations, data collection, or facts in to evaluate a particular situation. In other words, it is from specific to general. It is also called the 'rule developing' or 'bottom-up' approach. It is pointed out that without any form of explanation, learners can realize grammar rules with the help of this approach. From examples to rules- a simple path. Teachers who use this approach believe that induction, or learning through experience is a natural route for learning. In a language classroom, students are given texts and examples first. Rules will become evident if learners are given appropriate and enough examples. The role of the teacher is to provide the language and demonstrate the meaning to the class, provide more practice opportunities, and guide them to discover and realize themselves. When students are busy with practice, the teacher keeps silent. After extensive practice, grammar point is shown on the blackboard. Furthermore, students can discover grammar rules through several games, songs, or different interesting activities that require students' interaction and engagement. The retention of grammar concepts by using tips and techniques that are known to work in a

cognitively and make a strong impression on students' memory is the main purpose of this method.

In this picture, we can see that the inductive method begins with practice and ends with a theoretical basis. If teachers conduct lessons with this method, it can be one of the best assistances for students' mental and logical thinking. With the inductive method, students can improve their interactive and communicative skills. The second approach is absolutely vice versa to the inductive method.

The advantages of an inductive approach:

- * Student-centered lesson, active participation, attention, and motivation;
- * Discoveries, memorizing better, working in an independently;
- * Interaction of students and a teacher.

The disadvantages of an inductive approach:

- * Time and energy consuming;
- * Incomplete, you can have false conclusions, even if you have accurate observations;
- * A teacher should always have an accurate plan for the lesson.

***Deductive approach**

Deductive teaching is one of the traditional ways of conducting lessons in which teachers disseminate new information and rules about the target language, while students receive knowledge and, work alone using textbooks. In this approach, basic skills are the emphasis. At the end, students are assessed through a declarative testing system and, correct answers are distributed. This approach is usually utilized where the main target is to learn grammar. This approach involves grabbing learners' attention to grammar by instructing them on new content. It starts with explaining a new theme along with examples, which are followed by specific activities and tasks. They continue the process with practice. For instance, the teacher simply wants to explain the difference between past simple and present perfect: Firstly, one explains the rules and structures, then hand out worksheets where students are demanded to find which of them is suitable for sentences.

It can be seen that the deductive approach includes theory and hypothesis first. After fully analyzing-understanding the topic, we move into the practice part like observations and tests. Finally, all works are checked whether they are correct or not. This technique is generally for students who like accuracy and principles.

The advantages of a deductive approach:

- * It gets straight to the point, so there is no hesitation;
- * Time-saving, there is enough time for practice and application;
- * Guidance and process of the lesson continue accurately.

The disadvantages of a deductive approach:

- * Grammar presentation may not be understandable and attention-catching for some students;
- * Teacher-centered, lecture type of lesson less involves students' interaction;
- * It only assists to develop grammar knowledge, not in communication.

*** Eclectic approach:**

The last mode is an eclectic approach. It is the combination of all advantages of the two approaches mentioned above. It combines several teaching methods and approaches according to the needs of the lesson and learners. It plays the main role to break the monotony of the lesson. It does not include only one paradigm or assumption, instead covers different theories, styles, and ideas to gain knowledge in different cases.

The benefits of this approach are these:

- * Dynamic classroom atmosphere;
- * Variety in the classroom;
- * Every aspect of language is covered;
- * Assistance to students who have different learning styles;
- * Improvement of self-identity, autonomy, and freedom.

Such techniques, interactive games, and multimedia tool can be useful and works as parts of an eclectic approach.

RESULT

Method	Number of questions	Given time	Result
Inductive	15	30 minutes	78%
Deductive	15	30 minutes	81%
Eclectic	15	30 minutes	90%

Elementary school students were examined with tests related to grammar by masters. Before the test, they conducted lessons using these three methods by one professor. Then the test was prepared and presented to students. In terms of results, students could gain and memorize more knowledge by the eclectic method.

DISCUSSION

Numerous teaching ways are inevitably enhancing day by day in modernized and technological life. To form communication skills in the target language can be held with different strategies, but it is impossible to imagine learning a new language without its grammar. Most scholars argue that speaking with native speakers, and being in a language atmosphere can form language acquisition; however, speech with mistakes, and accent make sense. All children are not the same, they have special characters and skills that they cannot open to everyone. Most of them do not want to work alone, want teamwork instead. Learners need physical activities, and real circumstances to stimulate their thinking. Teachers need to use interactive tips to enthusiast students for a new topic. The more interesting the lesson is, the more they can learn. In spite of new trends and ways of language learning, grammar always keeps its importance as usual.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, every educator should consider all the peculiarities of students. Especially for school students, the eclectic approach is the most suitable one. The deductive approach is for primary school students, because they do not always realize the meaning of others. The inductive approach can help high school students in which all types of teaching methods can be experimented for them. The usage of a wide range of activities and instructional strategies will be useful for all learners generally. Personally, I would recommend the eclectic method for language learners who are already in this atmosphere.

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